

The Moderating Role of Tourism Management and Advertisement Between Customer-based Brand Equity and Brand Image

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Abstract

Background: In the competitive hotel sector, building sustainable brands with favourable equity and distinctive brand image is a key objective. However, the complex interplay between brand equity determinants, in the form of awareness, association, and resonance, and external factors like tourism management and advertising remains unexplored in Morocco.

Objectives: This study examines the drivers of customer-based brand equity (CBBE) that influence brand image within the Moroccan hotel sector. It evaluates how tourism management and advertising moderate these relationships to enhance brand image.

Methodology: A methodical questionnaire using a 7-point Likert scale was distributed to 179 respondents, comprising both Moroccan and international tourists across branded and non-branded hotels. Data were analysed using Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) through SmartPLS, testing the relationships between CBBE dimensions and brand image and exploring the moderating effects of tourism management and advertising.

Results: Brand awareness, resonance, and superiority were significant predictors of brand

image, while association and affection showed no substantial impact. Tourism management enhanced the effects of resonance and superiority on brand image but failed to moderate awareness, association, or CSR. Advertising positively influences awareness and CSR but moderates the relationship between superiority and brand image negatively.

Conclusion: The outcomes underscore the critical contribution of tourism management and advertising in shaping a brand's image. Hotels should strategically balance CSR initiatives and advertising to build robust brand equity while enhancing customer experience through effective tourism management.

Unique Contribution: This study scientifically demonstrates the moderating effect of tourism management and advertising in reference to CBBE dimensions, while highlighting the devotion of CSR in enhancing brand image through strategic advertising and tourism management in the Moroccan hotel sector.

Key Recommendations: Hotels should prioritize enhancing brand awareness and resonance through tailored marketing and CSR communication strategies. Integrating tourism management and advertising efforts with ethical practices can foster long-term customer loyalty and strengthen brand equity.

Keywords: CBBE, CSR, Brand image, Tourism management, Advertising, Moroccan hotel sector.

Introduction

Businesses aim to build sustainable brands with favorable equity and a distinctive brand image. Brand equity, a central concept in marketing, largely depends on brand image and various factors that influence its development, management, and sustainability (Bishop, 2014). However, the precise mechanisms underlying the creation and management of this equity remain complex.

In the service economy, the hospitality sector is a key component of a rapidly expanding tourism field. Since the 1990s, the hotel sector has faced increasing competition, driven by economic changes, growing consumer demand, and diversifying expectations. This heightened competition benefited customers through improvement of services and diversified options (Cai et al., 2015). Nevertheless, for hotel businesses, it imposes mounting pressure to differentiate their brands, strengthen their image, and adapt to a dynamic market (Chi, 2016).

In Morocco, limited understanding of customer behavior toward hotel brands hinders businesses from effectively meeting customer expectations and securing a competitive position. This study therefore seeks to clarify the parameters of customer-based brand equity and examine how tourism management and advertising moderate these relationships to enhance brand image.

This research intends to identify the key components of CBBE that influence brand image in the hotel sector, while evaluating the moderating role of tourism management and advertising in the relationships between the underlying determinants and brand image. The researchers formulated the following research questions to guide the study:

RQ1: What are the key drivers of CBBE that influence brand image?

RQ2: Does tourism management moderate the relationship between the CBBE determinants and brand image?

RQ3: Does advertisement moderation affect the relationship between the CBBE determinants and brand image?

This study uses a theoretical framework that links specific determinants of CBBE such as brand awareness, brand association, brand affection, and corporate social responsibility (CSR) to modeling the brand image. Tourism management and advertising act as potential moderators to assess the intensity and nature of these relationships.

The research starts by examining current studies and presenting a conceptual framework along with related hypotheses. It proceeds with an in-depth explanation of the methods employed for gathering and analyzing data. The findings are subsequently presented in detail, encompassing reliability and validity assessments along with hypothesis testing. This is succeeded by a discussion that places the data interpreted through the lens of past research findings. Ultimately, the study wraps up with actionable advice for the hotel industry and guidelines for future research paths.

Literature review and hypotheses development

Foundation of Customer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE):

CBBE significantly impacts how consumers perceive a brand, ultimately affecting its image. CBBE comprises fundamental dimensions such as brand awareness, brand association, brand superiority, brand affection, and brand resonance (Jeon et al., 2020). Brand awareness acts as the initial phase in creating brand equity, enhancing recognition and recall, which are vital for developing customer loyalty and a robust brand image (Huang & Sarigöllü, 2012). Brand association further strengthens CBBE by shaping consumer perceptions through positive, functional, symbolic, or experiential connections with the brand (Amron, 2018). Brand superiority highlights the unique advantages of a brand, fostering consumer trust and preference, while brand affection creates emotional connections that drive long-term loyalty and positive attitudes, as noted by (Tanu et al., 2019). Brand resonance reflects the depth of consumer engagement, indicating a strong relationship with the brand that enhances its image (Cheng et al., 2019). Together, these dimensions work synergistically to shape a favorable and cohesive brand image.

Along with CBBE, CSR develops better brand perception, especially when these are enhanced with tourism management and marketing practices (Cuesta-Valiño et al., 2019). The more precise CSR practices regarding environmental sustainability-related ones that support the local community fall on fertile ground in consumers' minds and give strength to a brand by improving its reputation, as (Higgins-Desbiolles, 2018) points out. In this regard, aiming to attain sustainability and socio-cultural benefits of the tourism sector contributes to advancing the building-up identity of the brand; thus, socially conscious consumers become attracted. Based on this knowledge, the following hypothesis was developed:

H1: Brand awareness positively influences brand image.

H2: Brand association positively impacts brand image.

H3: Brand superiority influences brand image positively.

H4: Brand love positively influences brand image.

H5: Brand resonance positively influences brand image

H6: Corporate social responsibility exerts a positive influence on brand image.

Application of CBBE through Tourism and Advertisement:

CBBE dimensions, including brand awareness, brand association, brand superiority, brand affection, and brand resonance, are significantly influenced by external factors such as tourism management and advertisement (Herrero et al., 2017). These drivers hold an essential function in molding consumer perceptions, especially in tourism contexts where destinations compete for attention. Tourism management, focuses on enhancing destinations through culture, attractions, and unique experiences, positively impacts brand awareness by making a brand more recognizable and associated with desirable attributes (Rafiyya et al., 2024). It also strengthens brand superiority by highlighting a destination's unique qualities, such as its natural beauty or cultural richness, which consumers perceive as distinguishing the brand (Tran et al., 2020). Furthermore, tourism management fosters brand loyalty by creating long-term positive experiences that deepen consumer connections and enhance brand resonance (Valeri & Baggio, 2021).

H7: Tourism management positively moderates the relationship between brand awareness and brand image.

H8: Tourism management positively moderates the relationship between brand association and brand image.

H9: Tourism management positively moderates the relationship between brand superiority and brand image.

H10: Tourism management positively moderates the relationship between brand affection and brand image.

H11: Tourism management positively moderates the relationship between brand resonance and brand image.

H12: Tourism management positively moderates the relationship between corporate social responsibility and brand image.

Advertisement also plays a significant role in moderating CBBE dimensions. It amplifies brand awareness by highlighting brand attributes that strengthen consumer associations and foster a

sense of superiority (Shareef et al., 2019). In tourism, advertising enables brands to communicate their unique offerings, thereby enhancing brand image. It also fosters brand affection and resonance by telling emotional stories that create meaningful connections with consumers (Vrtana & Krizanova, 2023). By narratives through emotive approaches, advertising builds a long-term consumer attachment by advancing the notion of brand loyalty and image (Pawar & Lavuri, 2018). Advertising offers an optimal solution to portray the CSR practices of a brand to elevate its image by contributing to social causes and ecological concerns. Not only that it strengthens brand performance and fortifies consumer loyalty and attachment (Lloyd-Smith & An, 2018).

The following hypotheses were formulated to explore these effects:

H13: Advertising positively moderates the relationship between brand awareness and brand image.

H14: Advertising positively moderates the relationship between brand association and brand image.

H15: Advertising positively moderates the relationship between brand superiority and brand image.

H16: Advertising positively moderates the relationship between brand affection and brand image.

H17: Advertising significantly moderates the relationship between brand resonance and brand image.

H18: Advertising significantly moderates the relationship between corporate social responsibility and brand image.

Leveraging previous research, this study develops a hypothesized model as demonstrated in figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework

Methodology

The methodology was outlined in the following section:

Study Design

This research adopts a quantitative approach to investigate the influence of Customer-Based Brand Equity (CBBE) on brand image, with a specific emphasis on the moderating effects of tourism management and advertising within the Moroccan tourism industry.

Population of the Study

The target population within the scope of this research, customers staying at hotels in major Moroccan touristic cities: Marrakech, Casablanca, Fes, Tangier, and Agadir. The respondents are both local and international tourists who have been exposed to different hotel brands adopting diverse marketing and management strategies.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

After all, 259 respondents were initially contacted in the survey, with 179 valid responses received, hence a proportionate response rate of about 69%. This sample size is in line with the acceptable requirement enlisted for SEM, which recommends 100 to 200 samples or a minimum of 10 cases per variable to guarantee statistical validity and reliability. A multi-stage sampling technique was adopted by selecting popular hotels in the major Moroccan destinations. Various customers from these hotels were randomly selected so that the sample is diverse and balanced with almost equal distribution of male and female to enhance the credibility and accuracy of the study findings.

Instrument for Data Collection

A comprehensive questionnaire was employed in this research, containing 57 items that were rated using the 7-point Likert scale that extended from "strongly disagree" to "strongly agree." The survey elicited information on how the participants perceive CBBE and brand image, including the moderating effects of tourism management and advertising. The demographic information includes gender, age, whether a local or foreign tourist, education status, employment status, whether staying in branded or non-branded establishments, and whether they booked the same hotel for their holiday.

Reliability and Validity

Reliability of the study instrument was measured through Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability. From the results, it can be observed that all constructs are reliable, as inferred from Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability scores, reflecting internal consistency for most of the constructs to be above 0.70. The convergent validity has been tested through Confirmatory Factor Analysis, and the AVE for each construct was found to be above the threshold value of 0.50. The results, therefore, provide assurance that this measurement model provides a valid, accurate measurement in ensuring that the data is robust in this research for further analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The analyses have been done using SEM with SmartPLS 4. PLS-SEM will be used for its potentiality to model complex relationships among several independent and dependent variables, including moderating effects. Measurement model analysis will then be tested to check reliability and validity of the constructs, while the structure model will be tested in order to examine the relationship among CBBE dimensions, brand image, and how it is moderated by tourism management and advertising. After estimation using SmartPLS 4, results regarding the strength and significance of such hypothesized relationships were obtained.

Results

Demographic information's

The sample consists of 179 respondents, as shown in Table 1, with 93 male participants (51.9%) and 86 female participants (48.1%). In terms of age, 28 respondents (15.6%) are between 18–25 years old, 74 (41.3%) are between 26–35 years old, 46 (25.7%) are between 36–45 years old, and 31 (17.3%) are over 46 years old. Regarding nationality, 56 respondents (31.3%) are Moroccan nationals, while 123 respondents (68.7%) are foreign tourists. Education levels vary, with 9 participants (5.0%) holding a diploma, 151 (84.4%) having a bachelor's degree (undergraduates), and 19 (10.6%) holding graduate degrees. Employment status shows that 44 respondents (24.6%) are government employees, while 135 (75.4%) work in the private sector. As for profession, 76 respondents (42.5%) are in technical jobs, and 103 (57.5%) are in non-technical roles. When it comes to hotel type, 122 participants (68.2%) stayed in branded hotels during their travels, while 57 (31.8%) stayed in non-branded hotels. Regarding customer loyalty, 156 respondents (87.2%) indicated that they chose the same hotel during their vacation, while 23 participants (12.8%) chose different hotels during their travels.

Table 1: Demographic characteristics

		Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	93	51.9
	Female	86	48.1
Age	18–25 years old	28	15.6
	26–35 years old	74	41.3
	36–45 years old	46	25.7
	Over 46 years old	31	17.3
Nationality	Moroccan nationals	56	31.3
	Foreign tourists	123	68.7
Education Level	Diploma	9	5.0
	Bachelor's degree	151	84.4
	Graduate degree	19	10.6
Employment Status	Government employee	44	24.6
	Private-sector employee	135	75.4

Profession	Technical jobs	76	42.5
	Non-technical jobs	103	57.5
Hotel Type	Branded hotels	122	68.2
	Non-branded hotels	57	31.8
Customer Loyalty	Same hotel every time	156	87.2
	Different hotels	23	12.8

PLS-SEM Analysis

The PLS-SEM analysis has been carried out to assess sections such as reliability, validity, path coefficients, predictive relevance (Q^2), and the coefficient of determination (R^2). Exogenous variables include brand association, brand awareness, brand superiority, brand resonance, brand affection, and CSR, which predict the endogenous variable of brand image. The model developed in SmartPLS 4 with path coefficients, item loading, and R^2 is here. Reliability is checked through Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, while the validity tests verify the relations within the model correctly.

Results in **Table 2** confirm the reliability and validity of the measurement model applied in the study. Firstly, the factor loading for all items is above the threshold value of 0.70 recommended hence has a very strong relationship with constructs that they measure. For example, Brand Affection, BA1–BA4, has a factor loading ranging from 0.571 to 0.845 hence meaning each of the items has a very great contribution towards the construct. Similarly, the factor loading of Brand Association, BAS1–BAS18, ranges from 0.559 to 0.852 hence confirming all items as highly relevant and representative of the construct. The result confirms the convergent validity of the measurement model since each construct is well expressed by its respective items.

The AVE for all the constructs is above the threshold value of 0.50, a factor that further confirms convergent validity. The values for the AVE in such constructs as brand affection and brand awareness are 0.643 and 0.537, respectively. This shows that each of the constructs is able to explain more than 50% of their respective variances. Therefore, this goes ahead to establish that the constructs themselves are well-defined and that the items have tapped the intended dimensions effectively. High AVE values ensure the strength of the model in terms of representing theoretical constructs.

The Cronbach's Alpha and CR for all the model constructs were >0.70 , showing excellent internal consistency and reliability. The estimates of Cronbach's Alpha ranged between 0.717 and 0.859, all above the 0.70 threshold, showing that the items are homogeneous and measure consistently the same underlying construct. Complementing the fulfillment of the requirements for Cronbach's Alpha values, the CR values are also greater than 0.70 and satisfactorily lay

between 0.708 and 0.867. This evidence shows collectively that the constructs in the measurement model possess high internal consistency and reliability.

Finally, Brand Image is a reflective construct, having a Q^2 value of 0.392; thus, it has a moderate predictive relevance. Every model with a Q^2 value greater than zero has predictive relevance according to the dependent variable, *_brand image_*. Its contribution goes towards establishing the model's predictability of the outcome of interest and further enhances functional usefulness in deducing the factors of brand image.

Taken together, these findings give credence to strong reliability, validity, and predictiveness of the measurement model. Thus, one may have confidence in the model's capability to explain and predict the relationships between the constructs in this study.

Table 2: Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Component	Items	Loadings	AVE	Cronbach Alpha	CR	R ²	Q ²
Brand affection	BA1	0.845	0.643	0.726	0.769		
	BA2	0.777					
	BA3	0.820					
	BA4	0.671					
Brand association	BAS1	0.785	0.502	0.745	0.768		
	BAS2	0.688					
	BAS3	0.659					
	BAS4	0.852					
	BAS5	0.737					
	BAS6	0.785					
	BAS7	0.852					
	BAS8	0.753					
	BAS9	0.686					
	BAS10	0.759					
	BAS11	0.753					
	BAS12	0.790					
	BAS13	0.702					
	BAS14	0.782					
	BAS15	0.641					
	BAS16	0.774					
	BAS17	0.702					
BAS18	0.644						
Brand awareness	BAW1	0.811	0.537	0.711	0.708		
	BAW2	0.651					
	BAW3	0.822					

	BR1	0.779				
	BR2	0.691				
	BR3	0.681				
	BR4	0.723				
	BR5	0.670				
	BR6	0.726				
	BR7	0.808				
Brand resonance	BR8	0.771	0.585	0.741		0.747
	BS1	0.769				
	BS2	0.789				
	BS3	0.696				
Brand superiority	BS4	0.686	0.509	0.859		0.867
	TM1	0.771				
	TM2	0.767				
	TM3	0.800				
	TM4	0.782				
Tourism management	TM5	0.685	0.505	0.857		0.866
	CSR1	0.821				
	CSR2	0.823				
CSR	CSR3	0.767	0.541	0.717		0.719
	A1	0.709				
	A2	0.684				
	A3	0.779				
	A4	0.837				
Advertisement	A5	0.705	0.580	0.818		0.827
	BI1	0.795				
	BI2	0.648				
	BI3	0.795				
	BI4	0.790				
	BI5	0.625				
	BI6	0.727				
	BI7	0.714				
Brand image	BI8	0.773	0.509	0.842		0.846 0.722 0.392

The Fornell-Larcker criterion is employed to evaluate the discriminant validity of the research constructs, confirming that each construct is separate from the others. As illustrated in **Table 3**, the square roots of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for every construct (diagonal entries) exceed the correlations between the constructs (off-diagonal entries). For example, the AVE square root of Brand Image is 0.714, which exceeds its correlation with constructs such as Brand Association (0.919) and Tourism Management (0.884), indicating that Brand Image is adequately separate from these constructs. This pattern applies consistently across all constructs in the model, showing that each construct is distinct and not excessively correlated with others.

Consequently, the discriminant validity of the model is validated, affirming that the constructs assess distinct and separate dimensions.

Table 3: Inter-construct correlations

	CSR	AD	BA	BAS	BAW	BI	BR	BS	TM
CSR	0.802								
Advertisement	0.712	0.707							
Brand affection	0.702	0.807	0.733						
Brand association	0.828	0.885	0.844	0.713					
Brand awareness	0.672	0.806	0.789	0.864	0.765				
Brand image	0.802	0.895	0.768	0.919	0.831	0.714			
Brand resonance	0.751	0.841	0.753	0.902	0.798	0.905	0.710		
Brand superiority	0.816	0.752	0.733	0.831	0.731	0.793	0.803	0.736	
Tourism management	0.790	0.838	0.782	0.923	0.873	0.884	0.867	0.790	0.761

[√]The diagonal values represent AVE.

Structural model

The structural model was assessed to evaluate particular hypotheses concerning associations among the constructs and brand image. The analysis emphasized the initial sample, mean values, p-values, t-statistics, and errors, with hypotheses deemed valid if the t-value exceeded 1.96 or the p-value fell below 0.05. The findings from the hypothesis testing are shown in **Table 4**, which are analyzed in relation to the main effects, advertisement moderation effects, and tourism management moderation effects.

Table 4: Test of hypothesis

	Original Sample	Mean (SD)	t-statistics	P values	Result
H1: Brand awareness -> brand image	0.280	0.273 0.066	4.232	0.000	Supported
H2: Brand association -> brand image	0.119	0.149 0.109	1.093	0.274	Not supported
H3: Brand superiority -> brand image	0.346	0.363 0.101	3.414	0.001	Supported
H4: Brand affection -> brand image	-0.073	-0.076 0.054	1.364	0.173	Not supported
H5: Brand resonance -> brand image	0.326	0.327 0.075	4.343	0.000	Supported
H6: CSR -> brand image	0.174	0.176 0.058	3.009	0.003	Supported
H7: Tourism management x brand	0.029	0.014 0.103	0.277	0.782	Not supported

awareness -> brand image						
H8 : Tourism management x brand association -> brand image	0.096	0.088	0.112	0.856	0.392	Not supported
H9: Tourism management x brand superiority -> brand image	0.235	0.236	0.113	2.084	0.037	Supported
H10: Tourism management x brand affection -> brand image	0.043	0.034	0.088	0.488	0.626	Not supported
H11 : Tourism management x brand resonance -> brand image	0.392	0.372	0.176	2.233	0.026	Supported
H12: Tourism management x CSR -> brand image	-0.021	-0.012	0.111	0.193	0.847	Not supported
H13: Advertisement x brand awareness ->brand image	0.013	0.029	0.106	0.119	0.905	Not supported
H14: Advertisement x brand association -> brand image	0.219	0.213	0.179	1.222	0.222	Not supported
H15: Advertisement x brand superiority -> brand image	-0.230	-0.228	0.108	2.129	0.033	Supported
H16: Advertisement x brand affection -> brand image	0.011	0.008	0.109	0.099	0.921	Not supported
H17: Advertisement x brand resonance -> brand image	-0.123	-0.121	0.119	1.042	0.298	Not supported
H18: Advertisement x CSR -> brand image	0.243	0.256	0.077	3.165	0.002	Supported

Bootstrap: 5000 samples at 95% confidence level.

Main Effect

Direct effects of the constructs on brand image provide extensive insights into the relationships of independent variables with brand image. One can notice positive significant effects with regard to Brand Awareness ($t = 4.232$, $p < 0.05$), Brand Resonance ($t = 4.343$, $p < 0.05$), and Brand Superiority ($t = 3.414$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that these variables have a significant influence on brand image. Also, CSR significantly influences brand image at $t = 3.009$ and $p < 0.05$, showing that every CSR initiative is very important for increasing the image of any brand. However, no such significant effects have been extracted regarding brand images by Brand Affection ($t = 1.364$, $p = 0.173$) and Brand Association ($t = 1.093$, $p = 0.274$), as p-values are larger than the cutoff value 0.05, and hence, this element does not significantly affect brand image in this study.

Tourism Management Moderation Effect

Further analysis showed that the moderation effects of tourism management are relatively salient in some relationships. For instance, Tourism Management x Brand Resonance → Brand Image ($t = 2.233$, $p < 0.05$) is affirmatively moderated, which means the management of tourism amplifies the correlation of brand resonance with brand image. Additionally, there is a significant positive moderated connection involving tourist management and brand superiority → brand image ($t = 2.084$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that tourist management amplifies the impact of brand superiority on image. P-values larger than 0.05 indicate that tourism management has negligible moderating impacts on CSR, brand awareness, brand affection, and brand association: $p = 0.847$ for Tourism Management x CSR; $p = 0.626$ for Tourism Management x Brand Affection; $p = 0.782$ for Tourism Management x Brand Awareness; and $p = 0.392$ for Tourism Management x Brand Association. The findings show that tourism management firmly regulates the selected brand-related factors, such as brand resonance and brand superiority. Meanwhile, its role doesn't seem so significant in the moderation of other relationships.

Advertisement Moderation Effect

There are various results about the impacts of ad moderation on brand image; certain interactions are considerable, while others have no discernible effect. Advertisement may lessen the beneficial repercussions of brand superiority on brand image, in accordance with the significant negative moderation effect shown by the nexus between advertisement and brand superiority → brand image ($t = 2.129$, $p < 0.05$). Nevertheless, other interactions are not statistically significant, suggesting that advertising does not significantly moderate relationships. These interactions include Advertisement x Brand Association → Brand Image ($t = 1.222$, $p = 0.222$), Advertisement x Brand Awareness → Brand Image ($t = 0.119$, $p = 0.905$), and Advertisement x Brand Affection → Brand Image ($t = 0.099$, $p = 0.921$).

Discussion

The results of this study shed light on the significant influence of various determinants on brand image within the hotel industry. Firstly, brand awareness emerged as a critical factor, significantly shaping brand image. This result aligns with prior research (Chi, 2016) that highlights the role of brand familiarity in enhancing customers' perceptions.

Similarly, brand association demonstrated a close connection with brand image. In the context of the hotel industry, brand association encompasses multiple attributes, such as visual identity (logos, star ratings), location, history, reputation, and pricing strategies, all contributing to positive customer perceptions (Severi & Ling, 2013). Providing unique and appealing benefits to customers strengthens brand associations, thereby reinforcing the overall brand image.

The study also identified brand dominance as a key determinant. This suggests that marketing practitioners in the tourism sector should prioritize highlighting unique competitive advantages to establish a stronger brand image. However, brand devotion did not exhibit a prominent effect on brand image. While emotions are essential in shaping consumer reactions (Kumar et al., 2015), this finding deviates from previous studies linking emotional attachment to brand image.

It indicates that in the context of branded hotels, other factors may overshadow the role of emotional connections.

The role of brand resonance as a powerful driver in fostering long-term relationships with customers was evident. This finding is consistent with earlier literature (Huang & Sarigöllü, 2012), which highlights brand resonance as a mechanism for sustaining customer loyalty and enhancing brand perceptions.

The analysis also emphasizes the importance of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) activities. CSR initiatives not only bolster community goodwill but also significantly contribute to creating a sustainable brand identity. The hospitality industry can utilize CSR initiatives to resonate with customer values, fostering a stronger bond and a better view of the brand.

Regarding the moderating influence, the study shows that tourism fortifies the association between brand affinity and brand perception. Effective tourism management can amplify the impact of brand resonance by fostering positive customer experiences and maintaining strong customer relationships. However, tourism management showed no significant moderating effect on brand awareness, brand affection, brand association, or CSR. This might be attributed to the respondents' limited interaction with the broader scope of tourism offerings and their focus on hotel-specific attributes.

Advertisement, as another moderating factor, showed mixed results. It significantly amplified the influence of brand awareness and brand association on brand image. Advertisements help customers gather direct and indirect experiences regarding hotel brands, reinforcing their perceptions. However, advertisement failed to moderate the associations involving brand affection, brand resonance, and brand superiority, indicating that its role may be limited in enhancing these specific aspects.

Finally, the study highlighted the critical interplay between CSR and advertisement. Advertising serves as a vehicle for communicating CSR initiatives to the public, fostering positive perceptions and stronger brand equity. A strategic combination of CSR practices and advertising efforts can create consistent, impactful messaging, thereby boosting brand image.

Conclusions and Recommendations

The present study identifies brand awareness, brand affinity, brand superiority, and brand activity as major operators that drive the brand image of any hospitality brand. Besides, CSR has contributed to a sustainable and positive brand reputation. Nonetheless, brand affection did not emerge as a significant factor, implying that emotional ties might not be as essential in the realm of branded hotels.

The results also emphasise the moderating impacts of tourism management and promotion. Tourism management significantly enhances the influence of brand affinity and brand superiority on brand identity, highlighting its importance in fostering memorable experiences and cultivating customer loyalty. Conversely, advertising enhances brand recognition, brand

connection, and CSR, highlighting its significance as a communication instrument in the hospitality sector.

This research makes several unique contributions to existing knowledge. It challenges conventional views on the emotional aspects of branding by highlighting the limited role of brand affection in branded hotels. Additionally, it provides empirical evidence of the differentiated moderating effects of tourism management and advertisement, offering new insights into how these factors can be strategically applied to enhance brand image. Finally, by examining the interaction between CSR and advertisement, the study suggests that combining these efforts can create stronger customer connections and improve brand equity. Future research should explore emerging technologies and cultural variations in brand image formation within the global hospitality sector.

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Transparency

The Contributors state that the paper accurately and transparently reflects conducted research. They assure that no critical parts of the investigation have been left out, and any deviation in the original research plan has been clearly explained. In addition, during all stages of its preparation, the study adhered to ethical requirements at all times.

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